

Local Administrations in Turkey Adaptation Process to The European Union

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Abstract

The European Union, which is sensitive to many problems including democracy, human rights, freedom of the press, and independence of the judiciary, stated that the important point in fulfilling these principles should be the construction of its own local government structures. This argument was based on the fact that the EU is sensitive to matters such as democracy, human rights, freedom of the press, and independence of the judiciary. In particular, the European Union, which seeks to exert its influence on the national governments of the candidate countries by means of Europeanization, promotes active political participation via the use of its economic framework and financial programs. Local governments of the European Union, on which the European Charter of Local Autonomy is founded, are the primary sites of democratic participation and decision-making. Many changes of local governments have been implemented in Turkey during the course of the lengthy process leading up to the country's entrance to the European Union. As a result of these reforms, the structure of local governments in Turkey has also been modified. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate, with regard to Turkey's municipal administrations, how the process of Europeanization interacts with monetary assistance. The Turkish viewpoint on the European Charter of Local Autonomy has been taken into consideration in this analysis. In addition, the issues that are included in the European Charter of Local Autonomy as well as the local government structure that is already in place in Turkey were investigated.

Keywords: *European Union, Turkey, Local Government, European Charter of Local Autonomy*

Introduction

The relationship that has existed between the European Union and Turkey for a considerable amount of time and has seen both highs and lows along the way has evolved into what it is now. Municipal regulation, much like a great number of other spheres, has been one of the primary focuses of Turkey's efforts to harmonize its laws with those of the EU. The process of globalization has resulted in information being more readily available. However, this

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accessibility has made contact across different cultures easier. Change and transformation have occurred in both candidate nations and adjacent countries as a direct result of pressure from the EU. Many people have used the term "Europeanization" to characterize this phenomenon.

The term "Europeanization" refers to the influence that European Union policies have had on the countries that make up the Union. These impacts are broken down into two distinct stages. At the EU level, the standards are enacted, and then at the local level, they are merged with additional standards. In the process of Europeanization, not only are official policies taken into consideration, but also fewer tangible characteristics such as attitudes and beliefs. The term originates from the widespread adoption, institutionalization, and systematic building of the political process. In this context, it is essential to avoid conflating the idea of Europeanization with other concerns like political regulation, integration, cohesiveness, and convergence, and to make clear the distinctions between each of these categories. Convergence is perceived as an outcome, yet Europeanization is understood to be a process in this context. At the same time, being more European does not always imply complete political union. However, European integration is necessary before any attempt at Europeanization can be made.

A. Local Government Reform

As a result of the tremendous acceleration of globalization that has taken place since the close of the 20th century, the dynamics of globalization, localization, and regionalization have started looking for answers to issues on an international scale. At the same time, the unchecked spread of knowledge compelled administrative bodies to decentralize by shifting their focus away from centralized organizations. In addition to the significance placed on global values, local values and projects were also accorded a significant amount of weight. According to Canan and Okmen (2009), there is a strong connection between the administration and the government, which has gradually evolved into a more efficient administration over time.

The Turkish public administration maintains its operations in accordance with the philosophy that governs the relationship between centralized and decentralized administration. Through curatorial oversight, we are able to strike a balance between centralized and decentralized forms of governance. The Ottoman Empire used a similar method of control over its subjects as well. They grew slow over time as a result of the effect of hyper-centralized traditions and

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bureaucracy, and they maintained their rule-based performance, avoidance of duties, and performance of paperwork to a minimum. At one point, this was the case. Since the 1980s, many different initiatives have been undertaken to improve the situation by reversing the process of change that has been produced by these challenges (Emini, 2009).

The building of the communities' infrastructure proceeded throughout the Tanzimat era and into the final quarter of the 20th century. When looking back at the early years of the Republic as well as the years that followed, it is clear that the process of reform has been a priority during this whole time. Migration from rural areas to urban centers has been on the rise since the 1960s. Examining the changes that occurred following the military intervention in the 1980s and the efforts that were made to strengthen the income and abilities of local governments during the time of Turgut Ozal are being looked at (Kosecik and Ozgur, 2005). This is being done so that it can be guaranteed that there has been ongoing political reform.

The growing comprehension of what is meant by the term "social state" makes a significant contribution to the restructuring of the allocation of roles between local governments and the federal government. This legislation resulted in a number of different transactions, as well as the transfer of some activities from the central government to the local governments, as well as certain operations from the local governments to the central government. The local administrations have reached a point where they are unable to execute their tasks in the requisite capacity and thus need reorganization. The capacity of local governments to adapt to the requirements of the age, to satisfy the expectations of the population, and to function more effectively and swiftly is declared to be the goal of the restructuring that is now taking place. Most recently, in Turkey, municipal administrations have been reorganized for reasons quite similar to these, and changes that are as comprehensive as they can be have been developed (Urhan, 2008).

Following the decentralization phase in both Turkey and Europe, the European Commission provided the following remarks in its 2004 Progress Report (Okmen, 2009):

"In June and July of 2004, the Turkish Grand National Assembly (TBMM) gave its approval to the comprehensive reform plan for the public administration. The Public Sector Reform Framework Law, the Special Provincial Administration Law, and the Metropolitan Municipalities and Municipalities Law are all part of this bundle. When taken as a whole, the goal of these four laws is to promote productivity while also dividing responsibilities and

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authorities across four distinct administrative aspects. It is anticipated that the effective implementation of this reform will make a contribution toward the modernization of Turkey's long-standing administrative heritage. This drive to change public administration is in accordance with the requirement of bringing it up to speed with modern practices and standards, which is the impetus behind the reform. If the reform movement in Turkey is successful, it will provide support to the country's attempts to join the European Union.

Law on the Fundamental Principles of Public Administration and the Process of Restructuring

The Basic Law on Public Administration was drafted in order to provide Turkey with a contemporary administrative structure and mindset for the 21st century. This was done in line with the social, economic, and bureaucratic transformations that have taken place elsewhere in the globe. The following goals for national and municipal governments, as well as their linked institutions and organizations, may be accomplished with the help of the law (Ozata Cetinkaya, 2012):

- The use of information technologies in the public sector, the simplification of laws and bureaucracy, the implementation of respect for human rights, result-oriented, accountability, transparency and participation,
- For the first time in the public sector, the basic principles that all public institutions must comply with are presented in a holistic manner,
- Strengthening the features of internal audit with a performance-based audit system,
- Creating interaction between the administration and resource allocation to all systems with strategic changes in management understandings in the public sector,
- Increasing the efficiency of the central government at the strategic level by clarifying the distribution of duties and powers between central and local governments,
- Closing the organization or function that is not needed or transferring it to the relevant departments on the agenda,
- Clarification of requirements to avoid duplication and distribution of tasks between institutions and ministries,

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- Bringing the institutional structure to a new efficient framework within a decentralized and horizontal organization.

The goal of the Public Administration Basic Law, which was drafted using the framework of this all-encompassing table, is to launch and guide the process of reorganizing the administration using a fresh and comprehensive viewpoint. According to Kalko (2010), the purpose of the legislation is to apply the notion of "good governance" in local and central administration in a way that is both comprehensive and long-term. This law represents a significant departure from the traditional approach to public administration.

Performance audits, financial audits, and evaluations to ensure regulatory compliance are often included in both the external and internal audits conducted in the public sector. As can be seen, the law that fundamentally reformed the administration also brought about a significant change from the principles of administration in the distribution of duties between the local and central administration. As a direct result of this change, the mechanism for public administration was completely reorganized (Ozata Cetinkaya, 2012).

In this context, one of the changes that will be made will be to reorganize Turkey's national structure and administrative system so that it satisfies the requirements of the European Union as well as those of the rest of the international financial community. However, the same process also includes globalist features since it makes it easier for global economic players to exist and function within the context of national arenas. This gives the process globalist qualities. In point of fact, these characteristics are comparable to the current globalization that has taken place all over the globe. According to Ozata Cetinkaya's research (2012), the law incorporates both the conceptual institutional networks and the guiding principles of global reform strategies.

This complaint, it should be observed, is quite similar to the criticism of new methods to public management. Having said that, it goes without saying that not every recommendation for a new management strategy as a new worldview is accurate. In other words, in the context of EU integration and globalization, it is not viewed as a viable choice to oppose the functional and structural reorganization of local and central governments as an administrative strategy or to develop universal standards for various categories in this respect. Both of these strategies are aimed at streamlining administrative processes.

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An essential legislation that prepares the way for the efficient operation of public administration is the Public Administration Basic legislation, which was adopted in line with the framework of the 21st century as an important statute. The opposition to the bill has been singled out for criticism in particular as a result of the permanent repeal of the statute. The provision of financial assistance for the reform by the European Union and other foreign organizations, particularly during the development of the legislation, contributed to an increase in the degree of criticism leveled against the law.

It has been argued that there is a need for structural change in the government. However, the actions that are to be conducted do not have to compromise the sovereignty of the nation, the system of a unitary state, the equilibrium between local and central government, and they must not go against the needs of public employees or the Constitution. All of these conditions must be met. The President, who first shared the public's objection to the legislation, later voiced his worries that his administration did not insist on the bill and that the law was not brought before the parliament again. He also shared the public's resistance to the measure from the very beginning.

Law Unique to the Administration of the Province

1913 saw the passage of a provisional legislation that would later become known as the Provision of Administration-i Umumiye-i Vilayet legislation. As a result of this circumstance, the groundwork for unique provincial administrations was put in place. After that, in 1987, the name of the preceding legislation was regulated as "Law on Special Provincial Administration" with the passing of Law No. 3360 (Hatipoglu, 2007).

In spite of the fact that the administrations of the Republic of Turkey have gone through numerous shifts over the course of their history, comparable studies have not been conducted on the basis of local administrations and special local administrations. As a consequence of this, these administrations have not had the institutional structure necessary to accomplish the goals they have set for themselves. The perspective that special provincial administrations are not self-governing institutions but rather institutions that provide development, public works, health, education, and other local services and report to local governments places these institutions under an excessive amount of scrutiny and control, which ultimately leads to their placement within local governments.

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The determination that local governments should satisfy the requirements of local governments is not entirely reflected in the Constitution's Article 127 because it does not fully comply with the decision. As a result, contrary to the current tendencies in the management of public services, special provincial administrations have never functioned as a general authority. During this time, the administrative capacity remained low, making it unable to deliver services that were both efficient and effective (Sen, 2009).

The Special Provincial Administration Law's main restrictions are based on a single structure existing within the state, administrative integrity enshrined in the Constitution, administrative decentralization, and central administration. Another thing that has to be taken into consideration in the bill is the general opinion of the European Union about the municipalities that Turkey has applied for in order to become members of the European Charter of Local Governments. As a direct consequence of these points of view, they attempted to write the legislation in such a way that it would include the fundamental tenets of local government, which are efficiency, participation, autonomy, and democracy. (Ozata Cetinkaya, 2012) The following are the four headings that are used to explain the rules that were implemented by the law:

- Interaction between special provincial administrations and central administrations,
- Authorities, responsibilities and establishment of special provincial administrations,
- Principles and principles regarding special provincial administration,
- Organization and elements of these administrations.

The localization of ministries such as "tourism, culture, forestry, environment, housing, public works, trade and industry, agriculture and health" is one of the service areas that the Special Provincial Administration provides. legislation No. 3360 was first the one to regulate the governor, and subsequently Law No. 3360 was the one to control the executive board; however, the new legislation modified this regulation. In conjunction with this differentiation, the sequence in which the organs appear has also been altered. The responsibilities of governors were modified to reflect their new roles as heads of local special administrations and representatives of legal organizations. It was said that the institution of the council presidency

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was introduced, and the presidency of the provincial council was removed from the governor. of the provincial council will be chosen by the council from among its members. the governor had previously held the position of president of the provincial council. The governor's responsibility for preparing the agenda for the parliamentary session was removed, and it was given to the president of the legislative session instead. Having said so, it is important to emphasize that the problems that the governor has presented will be given precedence on the agenda. According to the previous legislation, the assembly only met twice a year; however, under the current law, it is required to have at least one meeting per month in order to function as a permanent body (Ozata Cetinkaya, 2012).

Additionally, the statute enabled specialized provincial administrations to hire technical staff and specialists on a contract basis. It has been claimed that the special provincial administrative council would be responsible for making decisions about any and all forms of compensation for those individuals who will be working on a contractual basis within the parameters set forth by the Council of Ministers. It was also noted that performance requirements might be established for contractual workers, and that these individuals may be compensated appropriately if they met those standards.

Municipal Law

Local governments have, from the very beginning, transformed into not local government institutions that have the duty and authority to carry out local public services, but rather an entity that executes the duties that are allocated to them and is the extension of the centers. This transformation has resulted in local governments being less like local government institutions that have the obligation and authority to carry out local public services. It is more common to think of municipalities as centralized entities that provide development, public works, and other city services than as autonomous institutions administered by the people who live in the area. This administrative control included a wide range of topics, including finances, operations, employees, and organizational structure.

To effectively offer local government services, the present human and organizational structures of local governments are inadequate. The most significant barrier to successful service provision is an ineffective, bureaucratic, and inflexible organizational structure. As a consequence of this, municipalities have grown more susceptible to democratic rule since they do not exhibit the characteristics that are necessary for autonomy, like involvement, freedom of

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choice, and openness. It has been possible to deal with the regulations that were made by the law under four headings (Ozata Cetinkaya, 2012): • Establishment, authorities, and responsibilities of municipalities; • Principles and principles for municipal administration; • Organization and organs of these administrations; • Interaction between municipality and central government.

It is mentioned that the allocation of resources, authority, and obligations under the term of interactions between local and central governments is the most fundamental regulation that was brought about by the new Municipality Law. This is stated when we look at the rules that were brought about by the new Municipality Law. Municipalities, which are included in the administration on administrative tutelage and autonomy, do their business in line with the terms of the new legislation that was written into the Constitution. In order to guarantee that the responsibilities, organizations, and institutions of regional autonomous units are governed by law in a manner that is consistent with the fundamental decentralization, it is assured that this will occur. The local government still operates with its traditional president and council, since its tripartite structure has not been compromised. It has been established that the municipal committees will serve more in an executive capacity than in a decision-making capacity in the future.

In the sphere of local governments, one of the more recent understandings is to regard these governments as general authorities in terms of the quality of their services and the responsibilities they have, and to limit the number of these governments in order to increase the efficiency of local governments.

interact and collaborate with other state entities as well as non-governmental groups. There are certain services that are not required. These many alternate methods of service delivery help towns diversify their business operations, which in turn contributes to the municipalities' increased efficiency. The laws that will enable the development of flexible organizations, assuming employment policies suited for performance assessment and strategic management, are regulated in the legislation in order to build an effective management structure in municipalities. This is done so that an effective management structure may be established. A competitive strategy has been formed among local governments in terms of convenience and proximity in order to assure the efficacy and efficiency of service delivery (Arslan, 2009). This method was established in order to compete with other local governments.

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Metropolitan Municipality Law

One of the biggest societal shifts that has a major impact on how people live their lives and how society is organized is urbanization, which gained momentum in the latter part of the 20th century. Cities are defined not just as locations to live, find employment, and settle, but also as hubs of economic activity, cultural expression, and political power. After the 1950s, the concentration of the population in cities led to a growth in both the expense of providing services and the demand for such services.

The expansion of job possibilities brought about by Turkey's industrialization has resulted in the movement of people from rural regions to urban centers, which has accelerated the process of urbanization and led to a greater concentration of people living in urban poverty. In comparison to the eastern area, the western region has seen a greater degree of urbanization.

In order to address the challenges that come with living in a metropolitan area, several management strategies should be used here. Driving in a two-dimensional manner in urban areas has also become commonplace in several countries throughout the globe. In Turkey's metropolitan cities, a variety of administrative systems are now the subject of extensive research and study in preparation for their implementation. Reports of research on the reorganization of the public sector and blueprints for five-year growth reveal that large cities, particularly Istanbul, need for a distinctive approach to management.

In addition to the general understanding, the fact that the Municipality Law No. 1580 brought about the combined management of the special province administration and the Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality is the first of its type. It is required by law to have specialized kinds of control over big settlements, as stated in Article 127 of the Constitution of the United States of America. The first fundamental guideline for Turkey's municipal administration was finally enacted as a Decree in the year 1984. 2009 was also the year that saw the passage of Law No. 3030, which was titled "Amendment of the Decree-Law on the Administration of Metropolitan Municipalities."

The system, which did not come into existence until 1984 and was first implemented in the Law No. 3030, has a few flaws. There is a lack of objective criteria in the distribution of authority and duty, there are insufficient systems that will provide cooperation between administrative levels, the metropolitan administration is clearly dominant, and there is a lack of coordination

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and planning among the governorships (Kalko, 2010). These are the criticisms that have been leveled against the system.

It is said that legislation has been established in order to guarantee more effective administration of metropolitan cities by using the theoretical experience that has been gathered at the local level since 1984. This was done in order to ensure that metropolitan cities are better able to function. Within this framework, Law No. 5216 has established a connection between the formation of metropolitan municipalities and new guiding principles. According to Ozata Cetinkaya's research (2012), the purpose of this legislation is to accomplish the following:

- By assimilating the responsibilities of metropolitan municipalities, taking precedence over all other ministries and duties, ensuring that first-class municipalities meet all local ministries and duties,
- To provide the services and duties performed by the metropolitan municipality when coordination and planning is required in the metropolitan municipality,
- To determine the population conditions of 750,000 for the creation of a metropolitan municipality in a region,
- Establishing metropolitan district and first-tier municipalities,
- To regulate the issues that vary in terms of functioning and establishment of metropolitan municipalities, first level and district municipalities,
- To maintain the two-level administrative order in the form of the metropolitan and the first level under it, to develop commitments in terms of metropolitan coordination and control,
- Organizing the mayor's powers and responsibilities within the framework of principles such as compatibility, accountability, transparency, efficiency and effectiveness,
- To oblige the establishment of certain commissions in metropolitan municipalities,
- The metropolitan municipality has the authority to cooperate and plan throughout the metropolitan area in providing services,
- Assemblies meet regularly every month; they are a continuous assembly.

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Legally extending the boundaries of metropolitan municipalities enables their integration with local governments; nonetheless, it is essential to avoid deviating from the settlement concept in any way. In point of fact, the notion that the law is divorced from the concept of location is the source of the most damaging critique of the law (Tekin, 2018).

B. Elements of Local Government Reform

It is stated that institutional and legal regulations have an impact on regional and local administrations in European Union law and transactions. These domains are listed as follows (Ökmen, 2009):

- “European identity”,
- “Social and economic regulations of the European Union”,
- “The political union of the European Union”,
- “The local and central government relations of the European Union”,
- “Locality in the service provided in the European Union”,
- “Current content of public services of the European Union”,
- “Ensuring the development of the local economy in the European Union”,
- “Ensuring the effective participation of individuals in management in the European Union”,
- “Establishment of regional balance in the European Union”,
- “Cross-border cooperation of local units in the European Union”,
- “Representative democracy in the European Union”

Restructuring of local governments may be necessary due to specific dynamics occurring within such administrations. These internal dynamics can be explained as a lack of transparency, and they are characterized by structural change that is suppressed by external forces, poor performance, excessive curatorial control, allocation of central and local government resources, inability to meet age-related development needs, and personnel problems (Emini, 2009).

It is explained as an undisputed truth that this process is experienced as a reality all over the globe and that the impacts of globalization push societies towards becoming an information

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society. Globalization is characterized as a process for Turkey as well, and it is also stated as an incontrovertible fact that globalization is a process. The idea of "control," which encompasses democracy, participation, urbanization, decentralization, independence, and other phenomena of a similar kind, is one of the domains in which the process of transitioning into an information society may be affected either favorably or unfavorably by globalization. In the course of this procedure, Turkey has run across a few difficulties. According to Parlak and Okmen (2010), one of the new ways of thinking and values that evolved as a result of these problems was the need for reorganization and control.

The flaws that exist inside the administrative system are recognized as a requirement to be changed. This need is being pushed by the dynamics of the internal change. It is often believed that a country's current economic, social, and political climate are the root causes of its medium- and long-term difficulties. The need for change is the driving force behind the search for diverse answers to the challenges that have been presented (Emini, 2009).

During this process, the regulation was given a new organizational framework. According to Ylmaz (2015), organizational complexities and structural issues that disclose the nature of the issues may be summed up under the areas of bureaucracy and organizational culture difficulties, location and facility challenges, and so on.

The discourses of globalization, which have been applied to every region of the globe, have altered the nature of the tasks that are performed by local governments. These include the influence of foreign forces, privatization, and localization. It is vital to tackle financial difficulties, assure the involvement of municipalities and residents, and strengthen them via this reform of the work style in order for towns to be able to meet the tasks that have been placed on their shoulders. According to Emini (2009), there should be more focus placed on shaping the power that comes from outside the organization.

The reorganization of local governments is encouraged by external dynamics, legislative rules, globalization, the current economic environment, new approaches to public administration, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United Nations, neoliberalism, and other similar international players. The potential of a country to become an international nation is one of the benefits that a nation receives as a result of globalization. Localization is another benefit. According to Farazmand (2001), the role of global institutions is increased when a state operates on a worldwide scale.

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When it comes to developing efficient, dynamic, and up-to-date state institutions, the adoption of EU acquis is of utmost importance for candidate nations to work toward. Countries who participated in the process of harmonizing the acquis are obligated to put it into practice. Elements that are necessary for member states include conditions and principles for the legal control of local and central governments, as well as the operation of regions and administrative entities. The majority of legal rules are carried out by local governments (40-60%). These stipulations of the EU acquis call for a formalized legal framework. These rules are able to be summed up under the topics of "Consumer protection, public offerings, subsidies, local taxes, competition and environmental law, municipal elections, socio-political framework conditions, and municipal transactions" (Okmen, 2009).

The European Union is the most important external factor for the restoration of Turkey. The Council of Europe is in charge of establishing, controlling, and supervising the municipal sector of this process in Turkey, which is a member state that operates as a subsidiary of the EU. The European Union is not immune to the effects of globalization and is thus not autonomous from it. When local governments are reorganized, the whole national framework must also be reorganized to accommodate the new configuration.

The evolution of Turkey's ties with the EU has been impacted in some way by the administrative dynamics of the area. Given the circumstances, it was essential to put the law into effect on a variety of different concerns. The overlapping of internal and external forces, as well as the detrimental influence of internal elements on public functioning, made it essential to put changes into action in order to address the problem. The process of Turkey's entrance to the EU addresses a number of concerns, one of which is the need to improve the democratic character of the country's public administration while also working to increase its effectiveness and efficiency. In order to bring administrative practices into conformity with the criteria established by the European Union, changes have been implemented.

C. Use of the European Charter of Local Self-Government in Turkey

At the Sixth Ministerial Conference on Local Governments, the first item on the agenda was the presentation of the final text of the European Charter of Local Self-Government. The Council of Europe had been working on this document since the early 1980s. Throughout the course of these discussions, Turkey maintained that the European Charter of Local

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Governments should only be considered advisory. The European Charter of Local Self-Government has been approved by the majority of nations that are members of the Council of Europe. As a consequence of this, the European Charter of Local Self-Government was made available for signing by the member states on October 15, 1985, and it was discovered that the requirements of making the document available for signature did not conflict with any laws that were in effect in Turkey at the time. According to Yeter (1996), the Ministry of the Interior informed the Ministry of Foreign Affairs about the current situation.

On November 21, 1988 in Strasbourg, Turkey became the first country to formally embrace the European Charter of Local Self-Government. According to what is written, the European Charter of Local Self-Government was sanctioned by the Grand National Assembly of Turkey on May 8, 1991, with the passing of bill no. 3723. The European Charter of Local Self-Government was accepted by the Council of Ministers on August 06, 1992. On September 03, 1992, it was published in the Official Gazette, and on September 3, 1992, it went into effect (TR General Directorate of Legislation Development and Publication).

The following is a list of the nations that have signed the European Charter of Local Self-Government and approved it in their respective parliaments (Arakan, 2004):

- *Turkey,*
- *Sweden,*
- *Norway,*
- *Cyprus,*
- *Portugal,*
- *Liechtenstein,*
- *Greece,*
- *Italy,*
- *Spain,*
- *Iceland,*

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- *Malta,*
- *Germany,*
- *Luxembourg,*
- *Austria,*
- *Netherlands,*
- *Denmark,*
- *Finland*

Twelve of these nations have expressed qualms about ratifying the European Charter of Local Self-Government, but they have nevertheless done so. It has been said that Turkey, along with Liechtenstein and Austria, is one of the few nations that is pleased with the fewest things (Arakan, 2004).

Because of the approach taken by the central government in Turkey, many different things have been recognized with qualifications. Because the Regulation demanded that Turkey ratify at least 20 articles, the country only committed to ratifying those 20 paragraphs and made reservations for the other paragraphs. According to Cinik (2012), the majority of these reservations have lost their ability to be honored.

The goal for constant growth and change places additional duties and demands on local governments within the framework of democracy and localization processes that go hand in hand with globalization. This results in additional duties and obligations being placed on governments, which are in accordance with many contemporary ideas that are already contained in the European Charter of Local Autonomy or that need to be included in it. It is mentioned in Okmen (2006) that these alterations have turned into binding for Turkey and that Turkey is required to make alterations.

The institutions that make up the many parts of local government are broken down into several categories, but the most important of these categories is the municipality. According to Inac and Ünal (2007), municipalities in Turkey see the European Charter of Local Autonomy as an opportunity for the growth of municipalities to have an independent structure. This is considered as a chance for the development of municipalities.

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The third paragraph of Article 4, which Turkey ratified, outlines the fundamental idea of subordination. This is true despite the fact that the European Charter of Local Autonomy is not obligatory. The provision of public services should, in general, be the responsibility of public institutions, according to this notion. This notion was articulated for the very first time in a circular issued by the Prime Minister on January 28, 1992 (Yeter, 1996).

The European Charter of Local Autonomy is one of the information sources that is referred to on a regular basis in Turkey's process of passing laws pertaining to local government. During the legislative deliberations of the 59th Government, in particular, it was observed that the principles of the European Charter of Local Autonomy were taken into consideration, and it was stressed that this was taken into account (Cinik, 2012).

The European Charter of Local Governments will be consistent with the distribution of responsibilities between central and local levels of government. The issue of determining the powers and duties of the central government in order according to the charter, and reorganizing the rest by transferring them to local governments, is included in the book titled "Restructuring in Public Administration 1: Change in Administration for the Management of Change" dated October 2003, which explains the reasons for the reform. This book also includes the issue of determining the order in which the powers and duties of the central government are to be determined according to the charter.

The Law on the Principles and Restructuring of Public Administration, which governs the responsibilities, powers, and obligations of local administrations, had its name changed within the context of Article 8 of the draft. The new name of the law is the Law on the Principles and Restructuring of Public Administration. According to Kosecik (2007), the responsibilities and purview of municipal governments do not extend to the provision of any public services.

Countries run the risk of having their national integrity compromised. This problem, which arises for a variety of geographical, structural, and sociological causes, is of a greater significance for Turkey than it is for other nations. In addition, Turkey has implemented various adjustments in accordance with "Laws 5393, 5216, and 5302" (Alodal et al., 2007) as a result of the recent restructuring arrangements that were put into place.

Within the context of "Administrative Reform," it has been noted that since 2004, the Metropolitan Law No. 5216, the Municipality Law No. 5393, and the Special Administrative

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Law No. 5302 have been enacted in order to guarantee that local governments have financial and administrative autonomy. The aforementioned local government law is consistent, as well, with the European Charter of Local Autonomy due to the clear focus placed on autonomy within that legislation. According to Cinik (2012), laws that have been passed since 2004 have resulted in a relative reduction in the administrative authority that local governments enjoy.

In order to bring the new Municipal Law into conformity with the most recent version of the European Charter of Local Self-Government, a number of amendments have been introduced. In the legal language, it is stated that the legality control moves to the forefront of considerations. However, it seems that some provisions of the statute require aptitude examinations. According to Alodal et al. (2007), this kind of control is also referred to as a form of guardianship.

The 10-day waiting time that was necessary for local administrators to apply to the court and convey the decision of the municipal council to the municipality for approval was eliminated as a result of Law No. 5393. The administrative branches of states have evolved into information suppliers. In this respect, elected officials brought to light the principles of local democracy and autonomy featured in the European Charter of Local Self-Government (Urhan, 2008). The European Charter of Local Self-Government is a very significant and successful practice in the process of harmonization that takes place inside the European Union.

The public's ability to participate is subject to certain of these laws' constraints. However, they do not have any legal weight. For instance, the views of the residents are taken into consideration by the City Council; yet, the Council alone is responsible for making decisions about approval and assessment. It is said that the size of municipal administrations has greatly increased. On the other hand, Yuksel (2005) points out that the absence of legislation that contributes to an increase in their level of financial independence is a negative.

The unfettered discharge of one's duties and responsibilities are the component of legal certainty that is considered to be the most essential. In several European nations, the practice of laying off employees and dissolving towns has become widespread. The laws of these states include clauses as well, which guarantee that this will be the case. (Arkan, 2004) The study from the Council of Europe states that Turkey is the nation with the largest number of people who have been let go from their jobs.

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Both Law No. 5393 and Law No. 5216 outlined, in step-by-step fashion, the authorities that municipalities possess as well as their responsibilities. In keeping with the local administration method envisioned in the European Charter of Local Self-Government, the new legislation has established a significant number of additional responsibilities and authorities. These are enumerated in the following manner (Urhan, 2008):

- *Establishment of food banking,*
- *Regulation of urban traffic,*
- *The municipality's authorities, responsibilities and duties frame the municipal boundaries,*
- *Preparation of Geographic Information System and City Information System,*
- *Providing municipal services to the adjacent areas with the decision of the municipal council,*
- *The opening of protection houses for children and women in the Metropolitan Municipality and municipalities with a population of over 100,000,*
- *Providing municipal activities in the areas closest to the citizens and in the most appropriate way,*
- *Arranging the order of priority in the provision of services depending on the financial situation in the municipality and the urgency of the service,*
- *The municipality also performs other services and duties of a local common nature that are not given to other public institutions by law,*
- *Opening pre-school education institutions,*
- *Providing materials and necessary support to amateur sports clubs and students,*
- *Preparation of amateur sports competitions,*
- *Giving awards to the athletes who are successful in international and domestic competitions by the decision of the council.*

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C. Benefiting from European Union Funds by Local Authorities in Turkey

In order for member states of the European Union to be eligible for benefits like cohesion and structural funding as part of their membership, some minimum conditions need to be satisfied. This progress, which is primarily examined in the framework of the modernization of the administrative system, should be watched attentively for Turkey not only in terms of membership in the European Union, but also in terms of constructing a nation that is capable of performing its functions. candidate nations are eligible for benefits from the cohesion fund while they wait to become members of the European Union (Kaya et al., 2007). has taken part in the discussions being held in Copenhagen about the European Union. Within the parameters of the yearly progress report, research and studies in this area are conducted and analyzed. When the Accession Partnership Documents and Turkish National Programs that were produced in this direction are taken into consideration, there are a variety of issues that arise when looking at the policies and priorities related to local government, the environment, economic standards, free movement of people, justice and home affairs, social policy and employment, and consumer policy (Kosecik, 2007).

The European Union does not have the capacity to define the status of its member states' regional and local governments or the internal governance mechanisms of its member states. Nor does it have the authority to establish the internal governance mechanisms of its member states. The member states are the ones that are responsible for the organization of the various local administrations. Nevertheless, in many different spheres, regional and local governments are the ones that are tasked with being accountable for the implementation of the acquis of the European Union. In other words, regional and local authorities are an integral component of the system that makes up the European Union. They are burdened with the responsibility of putting European Union policy into action and persuading people of the initiative and validity of the European Union. Because of this, the degree to which the national, regional, and municipal administrations of any country that is applying to join the European Union is adequately prepared for membership is of the utmost importance for successfully meeting the requirements of the European Union and integrating into it. In this framework, it is vital to develop the capacity of regional and local governments in candidate countries, as stressed by the Regional Commission (Kosecik, 2008). This was one of the main points of emphasis.

When evaluating the effectiveness of the administrative reforms that have been put into place in our nation, it is essential to take into account both the nature of the change that was undergone

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by the local governments in the member nations of the European Union throughout the process of integration as well as the dynamics of that change. The integration process has repeatedly shown to be of critical significance for the municipalities of Europe. One may say that a specific procedure is followed by the national and local governments, as well as the political and administrative institutions that are engaged in this process. Local governments and the public sector are directly impacted by the regulatory framework that was introduced by the European Union (Arakan, 2004). This is particularly true with regard to the regulation of structural funds.

The following is a list of some of the fund programs that were deployed in Turkey during the years of 2007 and 2013 (Toksoz, 2013):

- *“Governance and Public Administration”*,
- *“Civil Society”*,
- *“Support for Compliance with the Acquis”*,
- *“Support for Union Programs and Agencies”*,
- *“Judgment”*,
- *“Fundamental Rights”*,
- *“Migration and Asylum”*,
- *“Integrated Border Management”*,
- *“Combating Organized Crime”*

Turkey has participated in many community programs to provide financial support from the EU. Participating in the programs with the status of candidate country, Turkey took place in the following programs between 2007-2013 (Aksu, 2019):

- *“Youth Programme”*,
- *“The Seventh Framework Program for Research and Technological Development”*,
- *“Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme”*,

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- “Progress Program”,
- “Cultural Programme”,
- “European Capitals of Culture Action for 2007-2019”,
- “Fiscalis 2013 Program”,
- “Customs 2013 Programs”

The programs that Turkey participated in the 2014-2020 period are as follows (Aksu, 2019):

- “Seventh Research Framework Programme”,
- “Innovation Programme”,
- “Customs Programme”,
- “Competitiveness Programme”,
- “Fiscalis Program”,
- “Competitiveness and Framework Programme”,
- “Cultural Programme”,
- “Progress Program”,
- “Lifelong Learning Programme”,
- “Youth Action Programs”

The initiatives and programs that are provided by metropolitan and local governments are surely how EU residents are made aware of the significance that the EU places on problems pertaining to local government and the help that it provides in this regard. On May 4, 2017, the Ankara Metropolitan Municipality hosted a meeting titled "European Union Funds for Municipalities" to discuss this topic. According to information found on the website milliyet.com.tr, Mehdi Eker, who served at the time as the Head of Foreign Relations for the AKP, highlighted the support that the regional council provided to the work that was carried out and said that it reinforced its links with the European Union.

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Research conducted as part of ongoing projects demonstrates that municipalities, particularly in urban areas, are able to carry out more productive research in the areas of "environment, human rights, participation, and capacity building" when they get funding and assistance from the European Union. In 2009, the "Household Waste Management for Environmental Sustainability" award was given to the Bursa Metropolitan Project in compliance with this framework. The budget for the project as a whole is 140.000 Euro, with the municipality of Bursa contributing 14.000 Euro and the European Union contributing 126.000 Euro. In the context of the project, officials from the Italian city of Turin met with Recep Altepe, who served as mayor of the metropolitan area at the time (www.bursa.bel.tr). These steps were taken in order to analyze the specifics of the project.

The Digi-Fire project was another endeavor that was evaluated in 2018 and found to be deserving of financial support from the European Union. The purpose of the project, which included a total of seven participants, was to give firemen working for the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality with a way of e-learning that was both quick and affordable for the purpose of enhancing their professional development. Within the framework of the project, the municipality was awarded a subsidy in the amount of 172,594 Euros; as a result, the municipality has made a significant step toward improving the capacity it already has (www.bursa.bel.tr).

In 2013, the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality successfully completed a project that was quite similar to this one. Within the framework of ATHENA, the development of technological solutions with the intention of assisting authorities in the production of useful crisis maps and the communication of information to people as quickly as possible in the event of a crisis is a primary objective. A financial contribution in the amount of 2.006.315.92 Euros was made available. Itfaiye.izmir.bel.tr is the website where the Department of Fire Brigade took its position as a participant in a multi-partner initiative on behalf of Izmir Metropolitan Municipality.

Cooperation between the Local Administrations of the Countries of the European Union and the Local Administrations of Turkey

It has been shown that one of the most significant consequences of the European Union candidacy and probable accession process on Turkish local governments is the creation and strengthening of collaboration between European Union member states and Turkish local

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governments. This has been proved to be one of the most important effects. (Kosecik, 2008) Some examples of this are collaborative conferences, initiatives that revolve on the sharing of ideas and skills linked to technical and professional education, and community service.

The Union of Local Authorities of Turkey is hard at work on important projects and research that are in line with the collaborative initiatives of municipalities in countries that are members of the European Union. On May 25, 2006, at an ordinary meeting of the Union of Municipalities of Turkey, various decisions were reached regarding cooperation with the unions of local administrations in countries that are members of the European Union as well as other international organizations that include local administrations. According to Kosecik (2008), the following is a list of the national unions of municipalities that work in conjunction with the Union of Municipalities of Turkey:

- *“Association of Spanish Municipalities”*,
- *“Association of French Municipalities”*,
- *“Association of Austrian Cities and Towns”*,
- *“Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions”*,
- *“Association of Municipalities of Slovenia”*,
- *“Scottish Association of Local Authorities”*,
- *“Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities”*,
- *“Netherlands Association of Municipalities”*,
- *“Helen Local Administrations and Regional Development Agency”*,
- *“German Cities Association”*,
- *“Finnish Association of Local and Regional Authorities”*,
- *“Danish National Local Government Association”*,
- *“Bulgarian Union of Municipalities”*

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Some of the local administrative units and specialized organizations of the European Union and the Council of Europe are as follows (Kosecik, 2008):

- *“Local Democracy Agencies Association”*,
- *“Southeast Europe National Local Government Associations Transport Network”*,
- *“Central and Eastern European Countries Local Authorities Cooperation Network Program”*,
- *“European Local and Regional Authorities Educational Institutions Communication Network”*,
- *“European Cities Association”*,
- *“European Council of Municipalities and Regions”*,
- *“Committee of Regions”*.

The "Municipal Partnership Network Project" is one of the projects that has been undertaken within the context of these decisions. This project is part of the collaboration between the Swedish Union of Regions and Municipalities and the Union of Municipalities of Turkey. Within this framework, beginning in 2003, the Union of Municipalities of Turkey has been engaging in a variety of interactions with the Swedish Association of Local Authorities in an effort to investigate the possibility of working together. In addition to the establishment of sister city contacts and the completion of collaborative projects, which were carried out between Swedish and Turkish municipalities, the "Municipal Partnership Network" project was offered as a viable option for an in-depth investigation.

Within the scope of the project, it was determined that five Swedish municipalities would develop sister city contacts with at least 15 Turkish municipalities and construct a communication and collaboration network in five different areas. In addition, the project called for the establishment of a network of sister cities in five different regions. During the course of the project, it was agreed that a network of partners would be established in the areas of financial management, municipal planning, regional economic growth, and environmental protection. On October 17-18, 2006, in preparation for the conference, officials from both nations met in

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Stockholm for a meeting that was conducted in preparation. During the discussion, goals were established for enhancing awareness on EU practices and boosting access to financing from the EU (Kosecik, 2008).

According to what has been disclosed, the European Union (EU) intends to initiate a robust conversation by forming relationships with a total of 423 communities as part of the "Sister Cities Project." On the list of European Union nations with which Turkey has the closest working relationships are Bulgaria, Greece, and Germany. The vast majority of these partnerships are being spearheaded by largely urban towns and districts. The metropolitan municipalities of Istanbul, Izmir, and Ankara were the ones with the highest notoriety.

The member states of the EU with which Turkey maintains the closest working relationships are graphically shown in Figure 1.

The EU Member States That Have the Closest Working Relationship with Turkey

2019 data derive from Aksu.

The graph in Figure 2 depicts the contacts that take place between the three major cities in Turkey and the cities of countries that are both members of the EU and candidates to join the EU.

Figure 2: Interactions That Have Been Formed Between the Three Largest Cities in Turkey and the Cities of Other EU Members and Candidates for EU Membership

2019 data derive from Aksu.

Research is conducted on "regional economic development, the concept of citizenship through geographical and cultural ties, and the motivation to become a global actor" for communities that have been proclaimed as sister cities and worked with one another. To put this into perspective, the fundamental dynamics of the partnership between Istanbul and Athens may be traced all the way back to the time of exchange. Activities in the realms of culture, society, and athletics also stand out, in addition to the most recent commercial connections. A sailing

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competition was proposed to take place between Istanbul and Athens in 2013, with the intention of bringing economic and sporting advantages to both cities. During the weekend of February 5-6, 2019, Greek Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras traveled to Istanbul. The periodically deteriorating connection between the two cities was given high priority during this visit because of its importance in bringing the relationship between the two cities to a higher level.

The collaboration between Izmir and Bremen in the 1990s formed the basis for Germany's attitude toward Turkish citizens at that time. In addition, during the course of history, a significant quantity of economic as well as cultural activities have been productive. In 2001, jobless young people from Bremen presented three yachts to the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality. These young people were looking for work. According to what has been mentioned on the website www.izmir.bel.tr, this circumstance will help to deepen the continuing partnership.

It is revealed that Sofia, a city that stayed under Ottoman administration for a significant amount of time, is one of the cities in Turkey that has historical and cultural assets. As a result of the city's abundance of mosques, madrasahs, masjids, and fountains, Turkish tourism has a significant impact on the Bulgarian capital of Sofia. Recent events, such as the "Bulgarian-Turkish Business Day" that was held in Sofia and emphasized the need for increased commercial interchange between the two capitals (www.trakyaka.org.tr), were successful in bringing attention to this issue.

CONCLUSION

Many people believe that the ability of local governments to successfully meet the expectations of their constituents for democracy and an increase in the degree of civilization is a sign of their effectiveness. Local governments have the major obligation of protecting the freedom and independence of people and the geography of the nation in which they live, as well as the task of finding solutions to social issues and difficulties relating to social life, and of constructing a system for democratically managing society. It is for this reason that it is believed that these local governments will build a structure that will secure public engagement and give citizen happiness within the state.

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Because Turkey has a long-established system of traditional government, the central governance model is the one that is most often favored. The institutions of the central government are referred to in the Constitution as organs and organizations with broad powers, while the institutions of the local governments are referred to in the Constitution as organizations with particular powers. The majority of authorities and responsibilities are assigned to the central government by the legislation. While carrying out their responsibilities, local governments are always under the watchful eye of the federal government. The activities of the autonomous government are also made possible by the provision of essential financial components by the central government. Because of this situation, the power of autonomy is increased even higher.

It is clear that ever since the Tanzimat era saw the development of local government institutions, the power, responsibility, and independence of local governments should have been strengthened in a comprehensive manner while the oversight of the central government was further reduced.

In the 1980s, people started making efforts to build municipal governments. Over the course of the last several years, significant efforts have been made to improve the functioning of the local administration. These studies in local governments are necessary as a result of the globalization process, which requires the state to become more locally oriented, and the administration to shift its focus to one that is human-centered. In order for this process of transition to be successful, administrations will need to let go of their old and conventional conceptions of leadership and simplify their thinking about the role. In addition to globalization, one other aspect that is considered as directing development and transformation in local governments is the changes that are happening in society as well as the link that exists between the local government and the people.

The phases as well as the impacts of transformation and change brought about by the process of globalization have been significant contributors to the development of an understanding of innovation. Studies on the process of joining the European Union have recently come to the forefront in order to enhance the variety of novel approaches to the administration of local governments. This is being done in an effort to promote diversity. Because of the European Union's (EU) interest in local governments and its focus on the notion of local in order to

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strengthen these governments and give them a democratic aspect, Turkey's local governments need to be restructured in order to fulfill the needs of this century.

The question of reducing the duties and powers of the central government in Turkey, which is a candidate nation for membership in the EU, and enhancing the performance of the local governments is becoming an increasingly important one. Turkey, which was nominated for membership in the union in 1999 and began discussions in 2005, has made progress in its strategy of EU integration and specified the stages that would be implemented in its national program. The EU has high praise for the efforts and research undertaken by Turkey in its progress report. The foundation of Turkey's public strategy and policy are the regulations that were drafted with this concept in mind.

The Metropolitan Municipality Law, the Special Provincial Administration Law, and the Municipality Law have all been drafted and approved in order to bring municipalities into conformity with the standards of the EU. These laws and regulations brought about substantial changes in the approaches used by local governments in Turkey. Furthermore, they redefined the obligations, duties, and authority held by local governments in an effort to eliminate impediments and challenges. The idea that the EU already has a system of local governments served as the basis for this legislation, which are based on plans for successful, value-added, and predictable local governments.

When one examines the justification for legislation pertaining to local government, one finds that these laws are bound by the European Charter of Local Self-Government. Therefore, the European Charter of Local Self-Government is beneficial from an administrative point of view. The EU's government is often referred to as the organization's constitution. Because of this, it serves as a general norm that is taken into consideration throughout the process of drafting and enforcing government laws. During this phase of the process, Turkey should not consider local government as a sub-branch of the central government, and instead should build its innovative methods on local government.

The lethargic bureaucracy in Turkey, together with the country's ongoing economic, social, and political issues, are the elements that slow down the pace of innovation in local governments. In addition, there are worries that regional activity would compromise the central political institutions of Turkey and exacerbate the disparities that already exist between Turkey's many regions. In a report on progress that was recently made public by the EU, it was said that if

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these issues were fixed as quickly as possible, it would be much simpler for Turkey to become more Europeanized. At the same time, within the context of the application for Sister Cities, one of the most essential aspects is to form partnerships and engage in promotional activities with a greater number of cities in Europe in order to find a solution to the issue and to foster a favorable perception of the area among the local populace. It is anticipated that the visibility of Anatolian cities, which now live in the shadow of three major cities including Istanbul, Ankara, and Izmir, will improve, as will the competitiveness of these cities in comparison to other cities. There is no question that this will lead to a greater degree of democracy. Consequently, Turkey is now participating in a significant process that will assure changes not only in the social, economic, and political domains but also in the sphere of administration throughout the course of Turkey's bid for membership in the EU.

The European Union appears as a supporting and occasionally compelling component in the transition that is being experienced in Turkey, which is a country that is seeing the repercussions of globalization. At the present time, the administrative duties of Turkey are subject to the transformations and changes that are taking place on a global and European scale, and it can be seen that the nation is undergoing a metamorphosis while simultaneously upholding its traditional values.

It is hoped that the innovative projects that are being carried out in respect to local governments would result in an EU harmonization process that is more effective, autonomous, and participative for local governments, and that local governments will conform to the European Charter of Local Government Autonomy. On the other hand, putting into effect the law that was drafted with this objective in mind is just as crucial as doing so. It is argued that the effectiveness of these rules is strongly tied to the adoption of the concepts originating from innovation by both local governments and society as a whole. When Turkey decided that it wanted to become a member of the EU, it did so with the understanding that there are numerous obstacles along this route and that, contrary to what is claimed and thought, it would not be successful in the near term. However, the results of the polls indicate that neither party is able to completely match the expectations of the other. The procedure is slowed down as a result, which also affects confidence between parties.

There is a rising sentiment among people living in Turkey that it is impossible for their country to join the European Union (EU), and this sentiment is spreading. The perspective of the

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European Union (EU) is one that condemns the manner in which the government treats journalists, representatives of local governments, advocates for civil rights, and independent organizations. It is believed that this mindset on the part of the administration is what led Turkey to fall behind in its process of Europeanization.

Even if the Turkish public's faith in the European Union has declined, there is still a significant amount of interest and enthusiasm for the process of Europeanization. Therefore, the degree of local Europeanization will continue to be a primary factor in determining Turkey's status inside the European Union, both from an administrative and a social perspective.

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